

Solvolytic Studies of Biguanides and Related Compounds

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Biguanides, guanylurea, guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ethers have been found to undergo solvolysis in methanol in presence of BF_3 as catalyst. The nature of chromophoric groups in the parent compounds and in the solvolyzed products have been interpreted from UV spectral data. Solvolytic studies in other solvents like ethanol, acetone and water have also been reported. On solvolysis, biguanides are converted to corresponding guanylureas and guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ethers to carboalkoxy guanidines.

The electrophilic nature of the simple boron compounds leads to the formation of coordinated boron complexes. Recently a review of coordinated compounds of boron-trifluoride has been published by Nikitina¹. Among the donor elements, nitrogen has been found to play an important role in BF_3 complexes and a detailed study of the coordination compounds of various nitrogen containing ligands such as amides, amines, anilines etc., has been made. Considering the presence of strong nucleophilic groups for coordination, it was thought that biguanide³, alkyl-biguanide, guanylurea, guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ethers, might react with boron trifluoride⁵ to form the corresponding boron chelates. A reaction between the ligand base and boron trifluoride-diethyl etherate in methanol gave no precipitate at ordinary temperature. The solution, on concentration gave the fluoroborates of their corresponding acid salts. However, the reaction at about -20° between biguanide base and boron trifluoride gave fine needle-shaped crystals having the composition L^+BF_4^- . The mother liquor on refluxing for a considerable length of time and cooling to room temperature deposited a white crystalline substance soluble in alcohol and acetone. This crystalline substance on elemental analysis has been found to be the fluoroborates of alkylguanylureas and carboalkoxy guanidines.

From the ultraviolet data it was concluded that the product is the fluoroborate of a guanidine derivative which has been formed from the solvolysis of the parent guanyl compound. The findings may be interpreted by taking into consideration the acid catalyzing characteristic of boron trifluoride in polar solvent

Some biguanide derivatives have been found by Kundu and Ray² to be susceptible to acid hydrolysis in aqueous solution. The present observation of BF_3 -catalysed solvolysis prompted us to study the properties and constitution of the transformed product. It is

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interesting to note that although the fluoroborates are soluble in acetone, the solvolytic reaction does not take place in pure acetone in absence of alcohol. The transformed products of biguanides do not give any complex compound with ammoniacal solutions of copper or nickel salts though in alkaline solution they give coloured precipitates like simple guanylurea normal salts³.

In order to arrive at a definite conclusion about the nature and constitution of the solvolyzed products, a study of the nature of the synthesised compounds of the corresponding guanylureas was considered desirable. The solvolytic reactions of biguanides and guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ethers take place in either of the following ways :

Curd and Rose⁴ prepared the substituted guanylureas (b) by hydrolyzing the corresponding dicyandiamide with dilute mineral acids or by refluxing equimolecular mixture of corresponding amine hydrochloride and sodium salt of dicyandiamide in aqueous solution. These guanylureas gave the characteristic coloured complexes with copper and nickel salts in ammonia. Since the hydrolysed products under investigation did not give any coloured complex with ammoniacal copper and nickel salts, it is presumed that the solvolyzed product differs in structure from those of Curd and Rose⁴(b). Kundu and Ray² first synthesized phenyldicyandiamidine (e), by fusing guanidine carbonate and phenylurea or urethane, which failed to give any coloured complex in ammoniacal copper or nickel salt solutions.

Our solvolyzed products behaving similarly are evidently of identical structure, with CO-group adjacent to the N-substituted group. In a hydrolytic study of biguanides Kundu

indication of the existence of identical chromophoric group in those compounds as is present in ammeline and guanylurea in neutral form. Hence from the UV absorption data it may be concluded that biguanides and guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ethers having $-C=N-C=N-$ chromophoric group undergo solvolysis at the terminal $-C=N$ -bond and the chromophore is transformed into $C=N-C=O$. These compounds like simple guanylurea show no bands at 220 nm in acid solution. From all these studies the solvolytic reaction may be written as :

EXPERIMENTAL

1. *Solvolysis of normal sulphates of biguanides³, alkylbiguanides^{3,9}, and guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ether¹¹ in methanol* : The substance in the form of its normal sulphate (5 g.) was taken in 40 ml methanol and the mixture was refluxed for six hr. in presence of 15 ml of boron tri-fluoride diethyl-etherate. After refluxing, the mixture was concentrated on a water-bath till all the alcohol distilled off. The mass left was then treated with acetone. Any insoluble sulphate remaining behind was filtered. From the filtrate the fluoroborate of the corresponding substance crystallized out on concentration over water bath. The solvolyzed product in the form of its fluoroborate was then purified by repeated crystallization from dry acetone.

2. *Solvolysis of the biguanides and guanylurea-*o*-alkyl ethers bases* : The free bases were prepared by refluxing the normal sulphates of the amines and sodium metal in methanol and filtering the insoluble sodium sulphate. The alcoholic solutions of the bases were then treated with $\text{BF}_3 \cdot \text{Et}_2\text{O}$ in the molar ratio 1 : 1 and cooled at salt-ice temperature. Fluoroborates of the original amines were filtered through suction and the mother liquor refluxed for six hr. The solvolyzed products were then crystallised after concentration of the solution on a water bath. It was then purified by crystallisation from dry acetone.

3. *Acid hydrolysis of Guanylurea-*o*-methyl ether normal sulphate* : 5 gms of guanylurea-*o*-methyl ether normal sulphate was refluxed with 150 ml hydrochloric acid solution (4*N*) for six hours. The hydrolyzed product was crystallized from the solution, washed with water, dried over fused CaCl_2 .

Ultraviolet absorption spectra : The spectra of the compounds were taken in alkaline solution in a recording Beckman DB spectrophotometer.

Methods of analysis : Boron was estimated acidimetrically after conversion to boric acid. Nitrogen was estimated by semimicro Dumas method. Fluorine was estimated as CaF_2 .

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TABLE I

Compound	Solvolyzed product	% of N		% of B		% of F	
		Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
1. Biguanidinium normal sulphate.	Guanylurea fluoroborate: $C_2H_6N_4O$, HBF_4	26.95	27.75	6.02	6.69	41.23	40.04
2. N ⁵ -methyl biguanidinium normal sulphate.	N ⁵ -methylguanylurea fluoroborate: $C_3H_8N_4O$, HBF_4	27.32	27.48	5.98	5.30	36.23	37.29
3. N ⁵ -ethyl biguanidinium normal sulphate.	N ⁵ -ethylguanylurea fluoroborate: $C_4H_{10}N_4O$, HBF_4	25.76	25.71	5.22	4.96	33.98	34.89
4. N ⁵ ,N ⁵ -dimethyl biguanidinium normal sulphate.	N ⁵ ,N ⁵ -dimethylguanylurea fluoroborate: $C_4H_{10}N_4O$, HBF_4	25.12	25.71	5.12	4.96	34.51	34.89
5. N ⁵ ,N ⁵ -diethyl biguanidinium normal sulphate.	N ⁵ ,N ⁵ -diethylguanylurea fluoroborate: $C_6H_{14}N_4O$, HBF_4	22.34	22.78	4.634	4.39	31.11	30.91
6. N ⁵ -phenyl biguanidinium normal sulphate.	N ⁵ -phenylguanylurea fluoroborate: $C_8H_9N_4O$, HBF_4	21.76	21.31	4.18	4.11	29.20	28.92
7. N ⁵ -benzyl biguanidinium normal sulphate.	N ⁵ -benzylguanylurea fluoroborate: $C_9H_{11}N_4O$, HBF_4	20.11	20.23	4.11	3.90	27.76	27.46
8. Guanylurea normal sulphate.	Guanylurea fluoroborate: $C_2H_6N_4O$, HBF_4	26.83	27.75	5.78	5.69	40.52	40.06
9. Guanylurea- <i>o</i> -methyl ether normal sulphate.	Carbomethoxy guanidinium fluoroborate: $C_3H_7N_3O_2$, HBF_4	21.02	20.48	5.63	5.30	37.87	37.29
10. Guanylurea- <i>o</i> -ethyl ether normal sulphate.	Carboethoxy guanidinium fluoroborate: $C_4H_9N_3O_2$, HBF_4	19.78	19.05	4.11	4.94	34.94	34.73
11. Guanylurea- <i>o</i> -isopropyl ether normal sulphate.	Carboisopropoxy guanidinium fluoroborate: $C_6H_{11}N_3O_2$, HBF_4	18.11	18.04	4.11	4.64	32.76	32.64
12. Guanylurea- <i>o</i> -isobutyl ether normal sulphate.	Carboisobutoxyguanidinium fluoroborate: $C_8H_{13}N_3O_2$, HBF_4	17.53	17.02	4.78	4.38	31.01	30.80
13. Guanylurea- <i>o</i> -methyl ether normal sulphate.	Carbomethoxy guanidinium sulphate: $C_3H_7N_3O$, H_2SO_4 , $2H_2O$	17.74	17.86	—	—	41.11	40.85

Sulphate %

DEBABRATA SEN AND AMARNATH MAITRA

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Errata

Vol. 48, 1971, p 1001, after the structural formula omit $n = 5$ or 6.